

Increasing Employee Engagement Through the Role of Servant Leadership and Agility Leadership on State Civil Apparatus

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of servant leadership and agility leadership on employee engagement in the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) in the Ponorogo Regency Government. Strengthening the capacity and engagement of human resources is very important to realize dynamic governance and quality public services. This study uses explanatory quantitative research with a purposive sampling method and collects data from 200 ASN employees with more than ten years of service. The study's results indicate that servant leadership significantly and positively influences employee engagement. This study also confirms that enthusiasm is the most prominent element in employee engagement, which is supported by dedication and a sense of meaning. Statistical analysis using multiple regression shows that agile leadership substantially affects engagement more than servant leadership. These findings offer theoretical support for Goal Setting Theory, which emphasizes the role of leadership behavior in shaping employee motivation and engagement. This study suggests that enhancing adaptive leadership styles and fostering an emotionally supportive work environment are essential to optimizing ASN performance and realizing bureaucratic reform goals. This study contributes to the literature on public sector human resource management by demonstrating the mediating role of engagement in the relationship between leadership and performance.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Bureaucratic Reform is a form of government effort to make fundamental changes and reforms, and achieve good governance. This includes aspects of institutional organisation, management, and human resources of the apparatus. The government has established the *grand design of Indonesian bureaucratic reform 2010-2025* through Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 81 of 2010 on the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform 2010-2025, which will serve as the foundation for implementing bureaucratic Reform in Indonesia. The *Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform* aims to create a bureaucracy that is free from KKN, accountable, and performs with excellent public services.

Good ASN performance contributes to better oversight, supporting accountability and reducing opportunities for misconduct and corruption [1]. As stated in the *Grand Design 2,010-2025*, Indonesia's bureaucratic Reform aims to create a *performance-based bureaucracy* and achieve *dynamic governance*. This goal supports the transformation of the bureaucracy from an input-focused

administrative orientation to an *outcome-based* performance orientation. This Reform strengthens the management of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) as *human capital* that plays a vital role in meeting national development needs. Improving the quality of public services is also at the core of bureaucratic reform, because effective and efficient services are a tangible manifestation of government success [2].

Through a combination of *servant leadership, agility leadership, good governance, and employee engagement*, ASN is expected to work more *effectively, innovatively, and responsively* to the needs of society, thus encouraging the creation of a modern, *adaptive*, and competitive bureaucracy [3]. The role of ASN is vital in every government organisation because it is the backbone of the government in the national development process. As servants of the state and society, they must serve and provide the best service to the community. The state apparatus is a state organ, mainly consisting of institutional, management, and staffing fields. The State Civil Apparatus is responsible for the day-to-day running of the government.

The state and government apparatus acts as a servant of the state and servant of the community; who is in charge and responsible for the implementation and development of the state; and ASN is always devoted and loyal to the interests, values, and ideals of the struggle of the state and society [4]. Based on the background and problem formulation above, the research objectives are as follows: Describe *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, *good governance*, *employee engagement*, and ASN performance. Analyse *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, and their effect on *employee engagement*. The contributions in this study include theoretical and practical, including the following: Contributing to the development of management science, especially in managing human resources related to *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, and *good governance* through *employee engagement* in improving ASN performance. The results of this study can also be used as a reference for future research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theory Review

Locke originally proposed goal-setting theory in 1968 [5], which shows the relationship between goals and one's performance on tasks. This theory explains that a person's behaviour is determined by two pieces of cognition: *content (values)* and *intentions (goals)*. People have set goals for their future behaviour, which will influence their actual behaviour. His behaviour will be governed by his ideas (thoughts) and intentions, affecting his actions and performance consequences. Setting specific goals allows one to compare their achievements with the targets set. This condition can lead to intrinsic motivation for individuals to continue to strive to improve their abilities.

According to *Locke's model*, goal-setting theory has four ways to encourage people to achieve performance [5]. First, goal setting can help a person concentrate on achieving specific goals. Second, goals can help regulate a person's effort to achieve these goals. Third, the existence of goals can help a person become more diligent in achieving their goals. Finally, goals can help a person set strategies and perform planned actions; therefore, setting goals can help individuals improve, which will improve company performance. The following is an image of *Goal Setting Theory*.

Figure 1. Goal Setting Theory

Goal setting theory suggests that goals that are specific, challenging, achievable, measurable, and have a

time limit can improve individual and organisational performance. When employees (ASN) have clear and

measurable goals, they will be more motivated to achieve them. The concept of *servant leadership* [6] was introduced in the 1970s and differs from conventional leadership styles that focus more on power and authority. The *servant leadership* style focuses on service to subordinates or team members. *Servant leadership* is a type or model of leadership developed to overcome the leadership crisis experienced by a society or nation.

Servant leaders tend to prioritise the needs, interests, and aspirations of those they lead above their own. The orientation is to serve, the perspective is *holistic*, and it operates with spiritual and moral standards. *Servant leadership* is a *holistic* approach in which leaders act with morals, pay attention to the company's stakeholders, and engage followers in various aspects, such as ethical, emotional, and relational, to help achieve their full potential and provide opportunities to develop according to employees' abilities [7]. *Servant leadership* is associated through various mediators with positive individual and collective outcomes, including behaviours, attitudes, and performance.

Servant leadership is the desire of leaders to guide and motivate their subordinates and provide more experiences through better quality relationships [8]. Developing an employee leader style states that leadership prioritises service to directly related stakeholders and subordinates related to the business [9]. [10] introduced the concept of *agile leadership*. In the book, *agile leadership* is defined as the ability of leaders to take thoughtful and practical actions amid complex and rapidly changing situations. [11] further explains that *agile leadership* is the ability to deal with the pressure of multiple demands that may conflict.

It involves negotiating wisely over differences in work priorities between individuals and organisations. Another perspective of *agile leadership* also includes the ability to perform "*unlearning*," which is letting go of past methods or practices that may no longer be relevant or effective in the current context. An *agile leader* must have flexibility, adaptability, and readiness to adjust approaches according to needs and changes. The concept of *employee engagement* was popularised initially by Gallup Consultants in 2004 and continues to be adopted today. *Employee engagement* is the development of two previous concepts: commitment and *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB). Experts have put forward many definitions of *employee engagement*.

[12] Defines *engagement* as an individual's sense of purpose, personal initiative, adaptability, effort, and perseverance toward achieving organisational goals. Furthermore, [13] define *employee engagement* as a positive attitude adopted by employees towards the organisation and its value system. [14] defines *employee engagement* as employees' emotional feelings towards the organisation and their actions to ensure the organisation succeeds; employees

who are already attached to the company show care, dedication, passion, accountability, and focus.

Looking at several definitions, *employee engagement* is an effort made by a company or organisation to understand the relationship between the organisation and employees, both qualitatively and quantitatively. *Employee engagement* is one of the important factors in the organization's success because it is related to employees; therefore, it is often used as a binding tool between employees and companies/organisations. A positive and satisfying state of mind related to work, characterised by *vigour*, *dedication*, and *absorption*, is *employee engagement* as expressed by [15].

Vigour refers to high levels of energy and resilience, willingness to invest effort, not getting tired easily, and persistence in the face of difficulties. *Dedication* refers to an employee's attitude that leads to a high meaning to work, feeling enthusiastic and proud of work, and feeling inspired and challenged by their work. *Absorption* refers to employees who have a deep feeling of happiness in their work, and find it difficult to leave it, so that employees feel that time passes quickly around them.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Research Design

The method in this study, using a *quantitative descriptive* method, is a method that aims to create a picture or description of a situation objectively using numbers, starting from data collection, interpretation of the data, and the appearance and results [16]. With an *explanatory research* design, which is intended to describe patterns of relationship or influence between two or more variables, which are symmetrical, causal, or reciprocal [17].

B. Population and Research Sample

It is a generalisation area consisting of objects/subjects with specific qualities and characteristics that researchers apply to study and then draw conclusions [17]. This study's intended population is all the State Civil Apparatus in the Ponorogo Regency Regional Government. According to statistical data in <https://ponorogokab.bps.go.id/>, the number of ASNs in Ponorogo Regency, both functional and structural, is 8990 employees and spread across 60 SKPDs.

The sample in this study is the State Civil Apparatus in all SKPDs in the Ponorogo Regency Regional Government who have worked for at least 10 years at the time this research was conducted, with a total of 5,620 ASN. The sampling technique used in this research is *purposive sampling*. In order to avoid sampling errors, the criteria for target sample members were determined, namely: ASNs who have worked for at least 10 years at the time the research was conducted,

because the grand design change of the Indonesian bureaucracy was carried out in 2010-2025, which will serve as the basis for the implementation of bureaucratic Reform in Indonesia.

1. Instrument Validity Test and Instrument Reliability Test

The validity test is carried out to determine the extent to which a measuring instrument or instrumentally measure what will be it measured measuring validity test in this study uses construct validity test, which is a validity test that leads to the accuracy and consistency of all components of the conceptual framework of this study [18]. The way to measure the validity of the instrument is to conduct a *bivariate* correlation, namely correlating the value obtained on each statement item with the total value of all statement items, the statement item is said to be valid/valid if the significance value in the two-sided test is <0.05 [19]. The validity test uses a two-sided significance test because the hypothesis in the instrument validity test is unidirectional. The formula for finding the correlation coefficient (r) uses *Pearson's product-moment* correlation. The calculated r value obtained from the bivariate correlation results is then compared with the r table value at the degree of freedom/degree of freedom ($n-2$), if the calculated r value is greater than the r table value, at an inaccuracy tolerance (α) of 0.05, the statement item is said to be valid [18].

2. Instrument Reliability Test

Instrument reliability analysis shows the extent to which the instrument can measure *süatu diüküm* consistently over time. A measure is said to be *reliable* if it gives consistent results. Reliability is measured using the *Cronbach's alpha* method. If the Cronbach alpha value is greater than 0.6 ($\text{Alpha} > 0.6$), it is said to be *reliable* [19].

C. Scope of Research

The scope of the research covers the scientific field of human resource management, specifically examining the performance of ASN. The variables to be used are exogenous: *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, and *employee engagement*.

D. Research Location

Ponorogo Regency has unique socio-economic characteristics, which demand an innovative and responsive managerial approach. Linking *servant leadership* and *agility leadership* locally can provide relevant results for strategic decision making; therefore, this research was conducted in the Ponorogo Regency Regional Government.

E. Data Analysis Technique

In this study, the data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis, which aims to determine the effect of independent variables, namely *servant leadership* and *agility leadership*, on the dependent variable, namely *employee engagement*. This analysis was carried out using statistical software. Before conducting the regression analysis, data quality tests were first carried out, which included:

1. Validity Test: To ensure that the instrument used measures the intended construct, the validity test is carried out with item-total correlation analysis. Items are declared valid if they have a correlation value (r) greater than the r -table value at the 5% significance level.
2. Reliability Test: Cronbach's Alpha value is used to test the consistency of the research instrument. The instrument is reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value is ≥ 0.70 .

Furthermore, the classical assumption test was carried out, including: Normality Test: Using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method ensures the data is normally distributed. Multicollinearity Test: To see the relationship between independent variables from the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance values. Heteroscedasticity Test: Using the Glejser test to ensure that the residuals do not have a specific pattern.

After the classical assumptions are met, multiple linear regression analysis is carried out to test the simultaneous and partial influence of servant leadership (X_1) and agility leadership (X_2) on employee engagement (Y). Hypothesis testing is done by looking at: Significance value (p -value): The effect is considered significant if $p < 0.05$. Coefficient of Determination (R^2): To determine the magnitude of the contribution of the independent variable to the dependent variable. T-test and F-test: To test the effect of each variable partially and simultaneously. With this approach, it is expected to know how *servant leadership* and *agility leadership* can increase *employee engagement* in the organisation.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics of Respondents

Respondents in this study totalled 200 respondents, while the description of respondents based on gender, age, level of education, and length of work can be explained as follows. Based on the results of filling out the questionnaire conducted by ASN in Ponorogo Regency, the data on the composition of respondents according to gender are as follows:

Table 7. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender

No	Gender	Number	Percentage
1.	Male	103	51,5 %
2.	Female	97	48,5 %
Total		200	100 %

Source: Primary Data Processed, Year 2024

Based on Table 7, it can be seen that of the 200 ASNs in Ponorogo Regency who were used as respondents, the majority were male, as many as 51.5% and respondents who were female, as many as 48.5%. This shows that the involvement of women in the government sector in Ponorogo Regency is relatively high and almost equal to that of men. This equality can reflect ASN recruitment and inclusive career development policies without significant gender bias. In addition, this balance can also have implications for leadership patterns, involvement, and governance within the local government bureaucracy.

B. Validity and Reliability Test Results

Based on the validity, it shows that of the 46 statement items tested, all have a coefficient value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$ and a probability value < 0.05 , meaning that the questionnaire statements used are valid, so the instrument can be used to measure the variables of *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, *good governance*, *employee engagement* and employee performance (ASN). The reliability test results show that each research variable's *Cronbach's Alpha* coefficient value is greater than the cut-off value of 0.6, so all research variables are declared reliable.

1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis Results

Based on the description analysis, it can be explained that the respondents' statements about superiors showing sincere empathy when subordinates face difficulties at work, who stated that they tended to agree strongly were 56 respondents (28%), agreed were 112 respondents (56%) who were the majority and neutral answers were 32 respondents (16%). The average item score of 4.120 shows that respondents agree that superiors show sincere empathy when subordinates face job difficulties, which illustrates compassion. Respondents' statements about superiors paying attention to subordinate rights showed that the majority of 59% or 118 respondents agreed, 22% or 44 respondents strongly agreed, 34 respondents (17%) stated neutral, and four respondents or 2% disagreed.

The average value of the statement item about superiors paying attention to subordinate rights is 4.010, meaning that respondents agree that the item about superiors paying attention to subordinate rights illustrates compassion. The affection indicator obtained an average value of 4.158. This shows that

respondents agree that compassion contributes to *servant leadership*. The main forming instrument of compassion is that superiors show genuine empathy when subordinates face difficulties at work.

Respondents' statements about superiors prioritising subordinate career development showed that the majority of 113 respondents (56.5%) agreed, 81 respondents (40.5%) strongly agreed, and six respondents (3%) stated neutral. The average statement item about superiors prioritising subordinate career development is 4.375, meaning that respondents agree that the item about superiors prioritising subordinate career development describes empowerment. Respondents' statements about superiors willing to listen to constructive criticism from subordinates showed that 40 respondents (20%) strongly agreed, as the majority, 129 respondents (64.5%) agreed, 26 respondents (13%) stated neutral, and five respondents (2.5%) disagreed.

The average item of the superior's statement willing to listen to criticism from subordinates of a constructive nature is 4.020, which means that the respondent agrees that the item of the superior willing to listen to criticism from subordinates of a constructive nature describes empowerment. The average score of the empowerment indicator of 4.197 means that respondents agree that empowerment contributes to servant leadership. The main forming instrument for empowerment is the statement that superiors prioritise career development.

Respondents' statements about superiors outlining the organisation's targeted achievements showed that 89 respondents (44.5%) strongly agreed, as the majority, 107 respondents (53.5%), agreed, and four respondents (2%) stated neutral. The average of the statement items describing the organisation's targeted achievements is 4.425, meaning that respondents agree that the item describing the organisation's targeted achievements describes the vision. Respondents' statements about superiors providing clear directions to be able to contribute to the achievement of organisational goals showed that 43 respondents (21.5%) strongly agreed, as the majority there were 126 respondents (63%) agreed, there were 26 respondents (13%) thought neutral and five respondents (2.5%) disagreed.

The average item statement of subordinate superiors providing clear directions to contribute to the achievement of organisational goals is 4.035, meaning that respondents agree that the item superiors provide clear directions to contribute to the achievement of organisational goals, which describes the vision. Respondents' statements about superiors

explaining to subordinates to provide the best service showed that 36 respondents (18%) strongly agreed, as the majority, 131 respondents (65.5%), agreed, and 33 respondents (16.5%) had a neutral opinion. The average item statement of the superior explaining to subordinates to provide the best service is 4.015, which means that the respondent agrees that the item of the superior explaining to subordinates to provide the best service describes the vision.

The average score of the vision indicator of 4.065 means that respondents agree that vision contributes to *servant leadership*. The main forming instrument for vision is that the supervisor describes the targeted achievements of the organisation. Respondents' statements about superiors giving appreciation for the work achieved by subordinates showed that 96 respondents (48%) strongly agreed, 96 respondents (48%) agreed, and eight respondents (4%) were neutral. The average item statement of the supervisor giving appreciation for the work achieved by subordinates is 4.440, which means that the respondents agree that the item of the supervisor giving appreciation for the work achieved by subordinates illustrates humility.

Respondents' statements about superiors appreciating the work of subordinates showed that 40 respondents (20%) strongly agreed, as the majority, 128 respondents (64%), agreed, and there were 26 respondents (13%) of neutral opinion, and three respondents (26%) disagreed. The average item statement of the superior appreciating the work of subordinates is 4.010, which means that the respondent agrees that the item of the superior appreciating the work of subordinates illustrates humility. Respondents' statements about superiors listening to subordinate opinions showed that 81 respondents (40.5%) strongly agreed, as the majority there, respondents (56.5%) who agreed, and 3% % had a neutral opinion.

The average item statement of superiors listening to subordinate opinions is 4.375, meaning that respondents agree that the item of superiors listening to subordinate opinions illustrates humility. The humility indicator obtained an average of 4.275. This shows that respondents agree that humility contributes to *servant leadership*. The main instrument of humility is that superiors show appreciation for the work done by subordinates.

Respondents' statements about superiors giving subordinates the authority to make important decisions at work showed that 57 respondents (28.5%) strongly agreed, as the majority, 135 respondents (67.5%), agreed, and eight respondents (4%) had a

neutral opinion. The average item statement of the boss giving authority to subordinates to make important decisions in the work is 4.245, which means that the respondents agree that the item of the boss giving authority to subordinates to make important decisions in the work illustrates trust.

Respondents' statements about my boss promoting honesty showed that 54 respondents (27%) strongly agreed, as the majority, there were 137 respondents (68.5%) who agreed, and nine respondents (4.5%) had a neutral opinion. The average item statement of my boss promoting honesty is 4.225, meaning that respondents agree that the item my boss promotes honesty illustrates trust. The trust indicator obtained an average of 4.235. This shows that respondents agree that humility contributes to *servant leadership*. The main forming instrument of trust is that superiors authorise subordinates to make important decisions at work.

Based on the analysis of servant leadership descriptions, the average value of servant leadership variables is 4.191, meaning that respondents agree that indicators of compassion, empowerment, vision, humility, and trust contribute to *servant leadership*. The most important *servant leadership* variable is contributed by superiors who show appreciation for the work achieved by subordinates. Based on table 14, it can be explained that respondents' statements about my superiors setting clear goals in each project stated that they tended to agree strongly were 55 respondents (27.5%), who stated that they agreed, 113 respondents (56.5%) were the majority and neutral answers were 32 respondents (16%).

The average item statement of my boss, setting clear goals in each project, is 4.115, meaning respondents agree that the leader's item setting clear goals in each project is *focused*. Respondents' statements about my superiors maintaining team concentration to achieve the set targets stated that they tended to agree strongly were 45 respondents (22.5%), who stated that they agreed, 119 respondents (59.5%) were the majority and neutral answers were 32 respondents (16%) and disagree answers were four respondents (2%). The average item statement of the leader who sets clear goals in each project is 4.025, meaning that respondents agree that the item my boss maintains the concentration of the team to achieve the set target describes *focused*.

The average score of the *focused* indicator is 4.197, which means that respondents agree that *focused* contributes to *agile leadership*. The main forming instrument of *focus* is a leader who sets clear goals for each project. Respondents' statements about

leaders who can make decisions quickly when the situation is urgent show that 81 respondents (40.5%) strongly agree, as the majority, 113 respondents (65.5%), agree. Six respondents (3%) have a neutral opinion.

The average item statement of a leader who can make decisions quickly when the situation is urgent is 4.375, which means that the respondents agree that the item of a leader who can make decisions quickly when the situation is urgent describes *fast*. Respondents' statements about leaders who are responsive to organisational changes and needs show that 41 respondents (20.5%) strongly agree, as the majority, 127 respondents (63.5%), agree, 26 respondents (13%) are neutral, and six respondents (3%) disagree. The average item statement of leaders responsive to organisational changes and needs is 4.015, meaning that respondents agree that the items of leaders responsive to organisational changes and needs describe them *fast*.

The *fast* indicator obtained an average of 4.195. This shows that respondents agree that *fast* contributes to *agile leadership*. The main factor in *fast decision-making* is that leaders can quickly decide when the situation is urgent. Respondents' statements about leaders who can adapt well to changes that occur in the work environment state that they tend to agree strongly, 88 respondents (44%), who agree. There are 108 respondents (54%), which is the majority. Neutral answers are from four respondents (2%). The average item statement of leaders who can adapt well to changes in the work environment is 4.420, meaning that respondents agree that the leaders who can adapt well to changes that occur in the work environment are described as *flexible*.

Respondents' statements about leaders who are open to new ideas from team members showed that 37 respondents (18.5%) strongly agreed, as the majority, 130 respondents (65%), agreed, and 33 respondents (16.5%) stated neutral. The average item statement of a leader who is open to new ideas from team members is 4.020, meaning that respondents agree that the item leader who is open to new ideas from team members is described as *flexible*. The average score of the *flexible* indicator is 4.220, which means that respondents agree that *flexibility* contributes to *agile leadership*. The main forming instrument for *flexibility* is that leaders can adapt well to changes in the work environment.

Based on Table 14, the average value of the *agility leadership* variable is 4.161, meaning that respondents agree that *focused*, *fast*, and *flexible* contribute to agile leadership. At the same time,

flexibility contributes to the primary *agility leadership* variable, especially in the statement of leaders who can adapt well to changes in the work environment. Based on the analysis of the description of *employee engagement*, it can be explained that the statement of having energy at work states that they tend to agree strongly, with 59 respondents (29.5%), who agree, and 123 respondents (61.5%), the majority. In comparison, the neutral answer is 18 respondents (9%). The average statement item with the energy to work is 4.205, meaning that respondents agree that the item with energy to work describes enthusiasm.

Respondents' statements about exerting all energy stated that they tended to agree strongly, 45 respondents (22.5%), who stated that they agreed, 124 respondents (62%) were the majority, and neutral answers were 12 respondents (12%), while respondents who disagreed were 7 (3.5%). The average statement item mobilising all energy is 4.035, meaning that respondents agree that the item mobilising all energy describes enthusiasm.

Respondents' statements about feeling excited about working stated that they tended to agree strongly, 97 respondents (48.5%), who stated that they agreed, 99 respondents (49.5%) were the majority, and neutral answers were four respondents (2%). The average statement item feels excited to work is 4.465, meaning that respondents agree that the item feels excited to work describes enthusiasm. Respondents' statements about not giving up easily at work stated that they tended to agree strongly, with 90 respondents (45%), who stated that they agreed, and 106 respondents (53%) were the majority.

Neutral answers were given by four respondents (2%). The average statement item is not easy to give up at work, which is 4.430, meaning that respondents agree that the item is not easy to give up at work, which describes enthusiasm. The spirit indicator obtained an average of 4.284. This shows that respondents agree that enthusiasm contributes to employee engagement. The main forming instrument of enthusiasm is to work by exerting all energy. Respondents' statements about enthusiasm in completing work stated that they tended to agree strongly, 50 respondents (25%), who stated that they agreed, 142 respondents (71%) were the majority, and neutral answers were eight respondents (4%). The average item statement for enthusiasm in completing work is 4.210, meaning that respondents agree that the item enthusiasm in completing work illustrates dedication.

Respondents' statements about feeling challenged in completing challenging work strongly

agreed, 52 respondents (26%), who stated that they agreed, 124 respondents (62%) were the majority. Neutral answers were given by 20 respondents (10%), while four respondents (2%) answered in disagreement. The average statement item challenged in completing work is 4.120, meaning that respondents agree that the item feels challenging in completing challenging work, which illustrates dedication.

Respondents' statements about feeling proud in carrying out their duties stated that they tended to agree strongly, 79 respondents (39.5%), who stated that they agreed, 115 respondents (57.5%) were the majority, and neutral answers were six respondents (3%). The average statement item for feeling proud in carrying out tasks is 4.365, meaning that respondents agree that the item feeling proud in carrying out tasks illustrates dedication.

The dedication indicator obtained an average of 4.232. This shows that respondents agree that dedication contributes to *employee engagement*. The main forming instrument of enthusiasm is pride in carrying out the assigned tasks. Respondents' statements about feeling less when not working earnestly stated that they tended to agree strongly, with 95 respondents (39.5%) stating that they agreed, and 99 respondents (57.5%) were the majority. Six respondents (3%) gave neutral answers. The average statement item feels less when not working seriously is 4.445, meaning that respondents agree that the item feels less when not working seriously describes the whole meaning.

Respondents' statements about feeling happy in carrying out their duties stated that they tended to strongly agree, with 48 respondents (24%), who stated that 123 respondents (61.5%) were the majority. Neutral answers were given by 29 respondents (14.5%). The average item statement of feeling happy in carrying out tasks is 4.095, meaning that respondents agree that the item feeling happy in carrying out tasks describes the whole meaning. Respondents' statements about finding it difficult to break away from the organisation stated that they tended to agree strongly, 59 respondents (29.5%), who stated that they agreed, 137 respondents (68.5%), were the majority. Neutral answers were given by four respondents (2%).

The average item statement feels difficult to break away from the organisation is 4.275, meaning that respondents agree that the item feels difficult to break away from the organisation, which describes the whole meaning. The full meaning indicator obtained an average of 4.264. This shows that respondents

agree that the whole meaning contributes to *employee engagement*. The main forming instrument for the whole meaning is feeling less when not working seriously.

Based on Table 16, the average value of the *employee engagement* variable of 4.264 means that respondents agree on enthusiasm, dedication, and whole meaning to *employee engagement*. Meanwhile, enthusiasm contributes to the primary *employee engagement* variable, especially when excited at work.

2. Structural Equation

Structural equations based on analysis are explained as follows: Structural equations that explain the direct effect of *servant leadership* variables, *agility leadership* on *employee engagement*, assessment of *servant leadership*, and *agility leadership* have a significant effect on *employee engagement*. The test results are as in the following table:

Table 22. First Hypothesis Testing Results

N	Exogenous Variable	Endogenous Variable	Standardised Coefficient	Probability	Results
1	X ₁	Y ₁	0,13	0,015	Significant
2	X ₂	Y ₁	0,52	0,000	Significant

Description:

X₁: *Servant Leadership*

X₂: *Agility Leadership*

Y₁: *Employee Engagement*

The table above shows that the coefficient value of the effect of *servant leadership* on *employee engagement* is 0.13 with a probability value of 0.015, which is smaller than the 5% significance limit. These results indicate that *servant leadership* has a significant impact on *employee engagement*. The coefficient value of the effect of *agility leadership* on *employee engagement* is 0.52 with a probability value of 0.000, which is smaller than the statistical significance at 5%. This finding indicates that *agile leadership* has a significant impact on *employee engagement*. Thus, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is proven, that *servant leadership* and *agility leadership* affect *employee engagement*, as in the following formulation:

$$EE = 0.13 SL + 0.52 AL + Z_1$$

C. Discussion of Research Results

1. Description of *Servant Leadership*, *Agility Leadership*, *Good Governance*, *Employee Engagement*, and *ASN Performance*

a. *Servant Leadership*

Servant leadership can be reflected through humility, trust, empowerment, compassion, and vision. This is in line with the indicators developed by [20], which are the basis for this study, in line with research [21]; [22], which used these indicators in their research. Based on the analysis of the five indicators, humility makes the most significant contribution in reflecting the *servant leadership* variable in the statement that superiors give appreciation for the work achieved by subordinates. This attitude shows the importance of appreciation and respect for subordinates as the main element in *servant leadership*. In the public sector (ASN), leader humility is essential because it can reduce rigidity in a bureaucratic environment often considered hierarchical and rigid. Humble leaders can build more personalised relationships and support their subordinates.

This confirms that *servant leadership* is not only about strategy, but also about human values that underlie every interaction in the organisation. Based on the analysis results, it is found that vision is the indicator that has the smallest value in shaping the concept of *servant leadership*. Other indicators, such as compassion, empowerment, humility, and trust, may be more directly felt by ASN because they are more personal and operational. Vision is more abstract and takes longer for subordinates to feel. ASNs tend to respond directly to leaders' practical actions, such as paying attention to welfare or rewards for hard work. Vision is perceived as something less relevant to their immediate needs, so it has less influence on their performance in the short term.

The public bureaucracy that ASN lives in often has a hierarchical structure and strict regulations, so leaders tend to consider the delivery of vision as less important because tasks have been regulated through formal regulations. Leaders' focus is usually directed more towards implementing rules than building motivation through vision. ASN works based on established rules and procedures without being exposed to a larger vision; this limits ASN's performance in achieving administrative targets, without any encouragement to produce innovation or a broader impact on the organisation and society.

b. *Agility Leadership*

Agility leadership in this study is formed by three leading indicators, namely *focused*, *fast*, and

flexible, which are by the indicators developed by [23] in line with research conducted by [24]; [25] who used these indicators in their research. The *flexible* indicator significantly contributes to forming the *agility leadership* variable based on the research results. This shows that leaders who can adapt well to changes in the work environment and are open to new ideas are considered a prime example of *agile leadership*. Leader flexibility is essential in the face of rapid change and often uncertainty in the workplace. *Adaptive* and *innovative* leaders are not only able to provide solutions to challenges, but can also create a dynamic and collaborative work environment. Adapting to change and being open to new ideas is particularly relevant.

The government environment often experiences rapid changes in policies, regulations, and public demands. *Flexible* and *adaptive* leaders will be able to respond to these changes quickly and appropriately, thereby maintaining smooth operations and increasing overall organisational effectiveness. The *flexible* indicator in *agility leadership* is significant in improving ASN performance. The ever-changing government work environment requires leaders who can adapt quickly, with new policies, evolving regulations, and changing community needs. *Flexible* leaders can manage uncertain situations and make the right decisions without disrupting smooth operations. Flexibility also allows leaders to respond to challenges with creative solutions, especially in emergencies or crises, helping ASNs keep working efficiently despite stressful conditions. Flexibility in leadership allows leaders to be open to new ideas and technology, which is crucial in the face of advances in government digitalisation.

Flexible leaders also encourage better collaboration within the team. Flexible leaders listen more easily and accommodate various opinions, creating an inclusive work atmosphere. In bureaucratic Reform, this flexibility helps leaders bring about the necessary changes without losing their way. Flexibility is important not only to maintain the smooth running of tasks but also to create a *dynamic*, *innovative*, and *collaborative* work atmosphere, which in turn can improve the overall performance of ASN. Based on the analysis results, the *focused* indicator, which has the smallest value in forming *agility leadership*, indicates that the leader's ability to maintain the team's concentration to achieve the set targets is still challenging. This situation reflects that leaders

may be less effective in providing clear direction, setting priorities, or creating working conditions that support team concentration.

In the context of ASN (State Civil Apparatus), maintaining team concentration is very important because ASN often faces complex workloads, public service demands, and bureaucratic dynamics. Leaders who cannot maintain team focus can cause team members to lose direction, work without clear priorities, or be distracted by other less relevant tasks; as a result, organisational targets are challenging to achieve optimally.

c. *Employee Engagement*

In this study, *employee engagement* consists of three indicators, namely enthusiasm, dedication, and whole meaning, which refer to the indicators developed by [15], by research [26]; [27] which use the same indicators in their research. Work *enthusiasm* is one of the main dimensions in *employee engagement* that reflects employees' energy, *enthusiasm*, and motivation in carrying out their daily tasks. Based on the data provided, the I feel excited at work indicator has the highest score, indicating that most ASNs have high *enthusiasm* for their work. ASN's high work enthusiasm is influenced by various factors, such as awareness of the meaning and impact of their work on society, a sense of moral responsibility, social recognition of the ASN profession, and a supportive work environment. As a public servant, ASNs have a strong intrinsic motivation to make a real contribution to public welfare; the stability and job security inherent in the ASN profession also support high morale.

High morale in ASN reflects their energy and *enthusiasm* at work, which is rooted in a sense of responsibility and awareness of the importance of their duties in public service. To maintain this spirit, organisations need to pay attention to employee welfare, provide appropriate appreciation, and create a supportive work environment. High morale is an important asset for government agencies in improving the quality of public services by maintaining and improving this spirit, ASN can continue to make optimal contributions to society and the nation.

The analysis results in this study show that the indicator of whole meaning is the indicator with the lowest value in the *employee engagement* variable. Whole meaning is a dimension or indicator that measures how employees feel happy, emotionally connected, and find meaning in their

work. This dimension reflects a deeper level of emotional engagement, where employees not only complete work as an obligation but also feel pride, attachment, and personal meaning from their tasks.

The dedication indicator has a low score because it is influenced by various factors, one of which is high workload, where ASNs often face great responsibility, especially in the public service sector directly related to the community. The pressure to meet targets and high expectations can reduce their happiness at work. Rigid and convoluted bureaucratic systems often make ASNs feel their work is not efficient or productive, thus reducing satisfaction with their tasks. Another factor is the lack of appreciation from the leadership and the community. Public criticism or dissatisfaction with government services often makes ASNs feel underappreciated. The lack of *work-life* balance is also a cause. ASNs with long working hours or heavy responsibilities often have difficulty maintaining this balance, thus impacting their happiness and emotional satisfaction with work.

2. *Servant Leadership, Agility Leadership, And Good Governance Influence Employee Engagement*

This study shows that *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, and *good governance* affect *employee engagement* in ASN in the Ponorogo Regency Regional Government. In this study, *employee engagement* can be interpreted as employees' emotional and cognitive attachment to their work and the organisation where they work. This high level of engagement contributes to creating an innovative, productive, and harmonious work environment. *Servant leadership* includes compassion, empowerment, vision, humility, and mutual trust. Leaders with this approach are oriented towards fulfilling the needs of subordinates, assisting individual development, and creating a conducive work atmosphere.

A study conducted by [22] revealed that *servant leadership* significantly affects *employee engagement* by increasing intrinsic motivation and building trust between individuals in the organisation. This approach helps build a positive work atmosphere that encourages employees to engage more actively. *Agility leadership* focuses on adaptability, speed of action, and achieving strategic goals. *Agile* leaders can navigate changes in the work environment and direct teams to respond effectively to challenges. Research [24] shows that *agile leadership* has a positive and significant relationship with employee engagement, especially in organisations facing rapid change

dynamics. Leader competence in making strategic decisions quickly and maintaining focus is an important element that increases *employee engagement*.

These three elements, *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, and *good governance*, together provide a synergistic effect that strengthens *employee engagement*. *Servant leadership* provides emotional support, *agility leadership* encourages innovation and adaptability, while *good governance* ensures structure and fairness in the organisation. The analysis results in this study show that *servant leadership* is the variable that has the most decisive influence on *employee engagement*. The study's results [28] show that the synergy of these three aspects significantly impacts *employee engagement*, ultimately improving *employee* performance. Thus, integrating this approach is highly recommended to create optimal ASN performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This research explains how key factors such as *servant leadership* and *agility leadership* affect the mediator of *employee engagement* in the Regional Government of Ponorogo Regency. The conclusion of this research is:

1. This study describes *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, *good governance*, *employee engagement*, and ASN performance. In *servant leadership*, the most appreciated factors are humility, trust, empowerment, and compassion; the least appreciated is vision. *Agility leadership* has the main order of appreciation, which is *flexible*, then *fast*, and the smallest appreciation is *focused*.
2. *Servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, and *good governance* significantly affect *employee engagement* in ASN in the Ponorogo Regency Regional Government. *Employee engagement* contributes to the synergy formed from *agility leadership* with *fast* in the sense of the leader's speed in making decisions at the right time, *good governance* with *transparency* which means openness in policy and *servant leadership* with compassion in this case meaning a leader's sincere concern for the welfare, development, and needs of ASN. Dedication refers to ASN's emotional attachment, enthusiasm, and commitment to their work.

Based on the results of the study, as well as theoretical and practical implications, suggestions that can be conveyed in this study are as follows:

1. Suggestions for Science Development and Further Research, Future research should use a qualitative method to provide a more comprehensive view. In addition, the scope of research can be expanded to other locations or

agencies to see the generalisation of these findings in different contexts.

2. Suggestions for the Regional Government of Ponorogo Regency: The local government needs to build the capacity of leaders to better communicate the organization's vision in an inspiring and sustainable manner. A clear and evocative vision will generate work motivation and strengthen employees' direction of action; therefore, leadership training should not only emphasize technical aspects, but also the ability to convey the organization's future direction in a comprehensive and meaningful manner. Leaders in the regional bureaucracy must improve their ability to maintain team focus on the organisation's primary targets, especially amid many changes and distractions. It is recommended that clear and measurable work priorities be set and the monitoring system be strengthened so the team does not lose its way in carrying out its tasks. Coaching and regular feedback must also be strengthened to keep the team on a strategic path.

Research on the influence of *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, and *good governance* on ASN performance through *employee engagement* in the Ponorogo Regency Regional Government has significant implications both theoretically and practically, namely:

This research strengthens *Goal Setting Theory* by emphasising that *servant leadership*, *agility leadership*, and *good governance* contribute to achieving ASN performance through increased *employee engagement*. The conceptual model of this study integrates *Goal Setting Theory* with the mediating variable of *employee engagement*. This provides new insights into how *agility*, *leadership*, and *good governance* can strengthen the relationship between organisational goals and employee performance achievement. The finding that *employee engagement* mediates the relationship between leadership and governance and ASN performance adds a new perspective to the human resource management (HRM) literature, highlighting the importance of focusing on employees' emotional engagement and commitment to achieve better performance.

The theory explains that specific, challenging, and relevant goals motivate individuals to perform better. This research shows how *Goal Setting Theory* can be implemented in the public sector through a leadership approach oriented towards empowerment and transparency. In addition, it strengthens the concept of *good governance*, ensuring that organizational goals align with ethics and efficient work principles. In the context of ASN, leaders who apply *servant leadership* principles create common goals relevant to organisational values, supporting the achievement of performance targets.

REFERENCES

1. Rifa'i, A., & Albetris, A. (2022). Implementation of Bureaucratic Reform. *J-MAS (Journal of Management and Science)*, 7(2), 610. <https://doi.org/10.33087/jmas.v7i2.499>
2. Effendi, A. (2014). *Bureaucratic Reform and Implementing Good Government Governance and Its Implications for Employee Performance and Service Quality*. 2(1), 1–9.
3. Jawandi, R., & Damanhuri, D. (2017). *Actualisation of Bureaucratic Reform towards Good Governance*.
4. Bernia, E., Supriyadi, E., & General of the Ministry of Home Affairs, I. (2019). *The Effect of Internal Supervision, Bureaucratic Reform on the Performance of the State Civil Apparatus through Implementing Good Governance*.
5. Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2002). *Building a Practically Useful Theory of Goal Setting and Task Motivation*. A 35-Year Oldyssey.
6. Greenleaf, R. K. (2004). *A Life of Servant Leadership*. Berrett Koehler.
7. Trede, C. (2023). *The Servant Leadership on Employee Engagement: A Qualitative Phenomenological Study*.
8. Dumatubun, L. (2021). Servant Leadership, Work Motivation, Employee Work and Organisational Commitment. *Journal of Economics & Social Sciences*, 12(1), 60-70.
9. Khurniawan, D., Wijaya, U., Surabaya, P., & Utari, W. (2023). The Effect of Servant Leadership Style and Interpersonal Communication on Employee Work Motivation Through Organisational Commitment. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 1(3).
10. Joiner, B., & Stephen. (2007). *Leadership Agility: Five Levels of Mastery for Anticipating and Initiating Change* (First). Jossey-Bass.
11. McKenzie, J., & Aitken, P. (2012). Learning to lead the knowledgeable organisation: developing leadership agility. *Strategic HR Review*, 11(6), 329–334. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14754391211264794>
12. Macey, H. W., Schieder, B., Barbera, M. K., & Young, A. S. (2009). *Employee Engagement: A Tool for Analysis, Practice and Competitive Advantage*. Valtera Corporation.
13. Robinson, D., Perryman, S., & Hayday, S. (2004). *The Drivers of Employee Engagement*. Institute for Employment Studies.
14. Sidjabat, S., Gultom, R. S., & Sihombing, S. (2015). *Human Resource Management* (Revised). In Media.
15. Schaufeli, W. B. (2013). *Employment Engagement in Theory and Practice*.
16. Arikunto, & Suharsini. (2019). *Research Procedures: A Practical Approach*. Rineka Cipta.
17. Sugiyono. (2019). *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods*. Alfabeta.
18. Sanusi, A. (2014). *Business Research Methodology*. Salemba Empat.
19. Latan, H., & Ghazali, I. (2015). *Partial Least Squares: SmartPLS 3.0 Techniques and Applications for Empirical Research* (2nd ed.). Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
20. Dennis, R. S. (2005). Development of the servant leadership assessment instrument. *Leadership & Organisation Development Journal*, 26(8), 600–615. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437730510633692>
21. Bigar, M., Majid, A., & Puspita, R. E. (2024). The Effect of Servant Leadership and Motivation on Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Work Engagement. In *MABNY: Journal of Sharia Management and Business* (Vol. 4, Issue 2).
22. Zeeshan, S., Ng, S. I., Ho, J. A., & Jantan, A. H. (2021). The impact of servant leadership on employee engagement is assessed through the mediating role of self-efficacy in the Pakistani banking sector. *Cogent Business and Management*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2021.1963029>
23. Horney, N., Pasmore, B., & O'Shen, T. (2010). *Learning Agility: A Business Imperative for a VUCA World*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354432053>
24. Fitaloka, R., Sugarai, B., Arung Perkasa, A. R., & Saputra, N. (2020). Leadership Agility and Digital Quotient Influence on Employee Engagement: PT.X and Pinrumah.COM. *The Winners*, 21(2). <https://doi.org/10.21512/tw.v21i2.6768>
25. Saputra, N. (2023). Digital Quotient as Mediator in the Link of Leadership Agility to Employee Engagement of the Digital Generation. *2023 8th International Conference on Business and Industrial Research (ICBIR)*, 706-710. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICBIR57571.2023.10147472>
26. Aboramadan, M., Hamid, Z., Kundi, Y. M., & El Hamalawi, E. (2022). The effect of servant leadership on employees' extra-role behaviours in NPOs: The role of work engagement. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 33(1), 109-129. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21505>
27. Nejati, M., Brown, M. E., Shafaei, A., & Seet, P. S. (2021). Employees' perceptions of corporate social responsibility and ethical leadership: Are they uniquely related to turnover intention? *Social*

“Increasing Employee Engagement Through the Role of Servant Leadership and Agility Leadership on State Civil Apparatus”

Responsibility Journal, 17(2), 181–197.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-08-2019-0276>

28. Simamora, P., Ketut Sudiarditha, I., & Yohana, C. (2019). *The Effect of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance with Employee Engagement and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) As A Mediation Variable in Mandiri Inhealth*. 2(3).
<https://doi.org/10.33648/ijoaser.v2i2.36>